

IPBES Value Assessment

SEARCH TERMS CH3_CH4

SYSTEMATIC REVIEW (PCIV (CH3) & VALUATION UPTAKE (CH4))

May 2020

Inquiries:

Mette Termansen mt@ifro.ku.dk
David Barton david.barton@nina.no
Aidin Niamir niamir@gmail.com

The logic of the key words is that the paper should be i) about nature or biodiversity, ii) should be an application of a valuation method/approach, iii) should focus on at least one of the value dimensions that we work with in the assessment (mainly identified in Ch2), iv) has the purpose to support decision-making (understood in a broad sense).

The list of KEY WORDS below are the new search terms to identify papers for the PCIV review:

To be selected for a review a paper has to include a combination of the search terms in the NATURE& DIVERSITY list, the PURPOSE list, the VALUE list and the METHODS list in the titles, key words or abstracts of the paper.

A corpus was also identified for ch4 valuation uptake review, excluding the PURPOSE typology list.

Chapter 4 has decided not to sample from “purpose typology” words.

ID	Name	TS
1	Values = #1 #2 OR #3 OR #4	TS=(wellbeing OR welfare OR well-being OR utilit* OR "quality of life" OR "willingness-to-pay" OR "willingness to pay" OR WTP OR "willingness-to-accept" OR WTA OR "willingness to accept" OR "human-nature relat*" OR "society-nature relat*" OR "ecosystem servi*" OR "environmental servi*" OR "intrinsic valu*" OR "relational valu*" OR "cultural valu*" OR "instrumental valu*" OR "option valu*" OR "insurance valu*" OR "bequest valu*" OR "indirect valu*" OR "existence valu*" OR "non-use valu*" OR "direct use val*" OR biocentrism OR "ecosystem function*" OR "ecosystem process*" OR "ecological resilience" OR "genetic diversity" OR "functional diversity" OR "taxonomic diversity" OR "phylogenetic diversity" OR "embodied energy" OR "genetic resource*" OR "Human Appropriation of Net Primary Production" OR HANPP OR "carbon footprint" OR "water footprint" OR "environmental footprint" OR "ecological footprint" OR "habitat quality" OR "habitat for" OR "biodiversity" OR "regulating service*" OR "climate regulation" OR "regulation of water*" OR pollination OR "biological control" OR "water quality" OR "air quality" OR "flood control" OR "provisioning service*" OR "cultural service*" OR "ecotourism" OR "ascribed valu*" OR "held valu*" OR "psychological benefits" OR "food security" OR "water security" OR "energy security" OR "social-ecological resilience" OR "social resilience" OR "social sustainability" OR "economic sustainability" OR "ecological sustainability" OR "biocultural diversity" OR "diversity of * options" OR "sense of place" OR "sense of community" OR "intra-generational equity" OR "inter-generational equity" OR "environmental justice" OR "mental health" OR "physical health" OR "economic valu*" OR "social valu*" OR "socio-cultural val*" OR happiness OR "recreation*" OR "amenity" OR "outdoor" OR "non-timber product*" OR "fuelwood" OR "charcoal" OR "subsistence" OR "timber" OR "natures contributions to people" OR "benefit* to people" OR "benefit* to humans" OR "NCP" OR "ecosystem service*" OR "disservice" OR "well being" OR "income" OR "poverty" OR "human well*" OR "nutrition" OR "livelihood*" OR "security" OR "vulnerab*" OR "social capital" OR "human capital" OR "asset*" OR "social welfare" OR "poor communit*" OR "poor people" OR "indigenous people*" OR "well living" OR "living standard*" OR "life satisfaction" OR prosperity OR progress OR "needs fulfillment" OR "development" OR "empowerment" OR "capabilit*" OR "happiness" OR "nutrition* intake" OR "carbon sequestration" OR sovereignty OR kinship OR reciprocity OR altruism OR altruistic OR "shared valu*" OR "spiritual valu*" OR "religious valu*" OR stewardship OR "rights of nature" OR "Mother Earth")
2	VALUES_INSTRUMENTAL	TS=(wellbeing OR welfare OR well-being OR utilit* OR "willingness-to-pay" OR "willingness to pay" OR WTP OR "willingness-to-accept" OR WTA OR "willingness to accept" OR "ecosystem service" OR "instrumental valu*" OR "option valu*" OR "insurance valu*" OR "indirect valu*" OR "existence valu*" OR "non-use valu*" OR "direct use val*" OR "regulating service*" OR "climate regulation" OR "regulation of climate" OR "regulation of water*" OR pollination OR "biological control" OR "medicinal resource*" OR "water quality" OR "air quality" OR "flood control" OR "provisioning service*" OR "cultural service*" OR "ecotourism" OR "ascribed valu*" OR "food security" OR "water security" OR "energy security" OR "economic sustainability" OR "diversity of * options" OR "economic valu*" OR happiness OR "recreation*" OR "amenity" OR "outdoor" OR "non-timber product*" OR "fuelwood" OR "charcoal" OR "subsistence" OR "timber" OR "natures contributions to people" OR "benefit* to people" OR "benefit* to humans" OR "NCP" OR "ecosystem service*" OR "disservice" OR "well being" OR "income" OR "poverty" OR "human well*" OR "nutrition" OR "livelihood*" OR "security" OR "vulnerab*" OR "human capital" OR "asset*" OR "social welfare" OR "poor communit*" OR "poor people" OR "well living" OR "living standard*" OR "life satisfaction" OR prosperity OR progress OR "needs fulfillment" OR "development" OR "happiness" OR "nutrition* intake" OR "carbon sequestration")
3	VALUES_INTRINSIC	TS=("intrinsic valu*" OR biocentrism OR "ecosystem function*" OR "ecosystem process*" OR "ecological resilience" OR "genetic diversity" OR "functional diversity" OR "taxonomic diversity" OR "phylogenetic diversity" OR "embodied energy" OR "genetic resource*" OR "Human Appropriation of Net Primary Production" OR HANPP OR "carbon footprint" OR "water footprint" OR "environmental footprint" OR "ecological footprint" OR "habitat quality" OR "habitat for" OR "biodiversity" OR "ecological sustainability" OR "Mother Earth" OR "held valu*")
4	VALUES_RELATIONAL	TS=("quality of life" OR "human-nature relat*" OR "society-nature relat*" OR "relational valu*" OR "cultural valu*" OR "psychological benefits" OR "social-ecological resilience" OR "social resilience" OR "social sustainability" OR "biocultural diversity" OR "sense of place" OR "sense of community" OR "intra-generational equity" OR "inter-generational equity" OR "environmental justice" OR "mental health" OR "physical health" OR "social valu*" OR "socio-cultural val*" "social capital" OR "indigenous people*" OR "empowerment" OR "capabilit*" OR sovereignty OR kinship OR reciprocity OR altruis* OR "bequest valu*")
5	METHODS = #5 = #6 OR #7 OR #8 OR #9 OR #10 OR #11	TS = (Valuation OR WTP OR "willingness to pay" OR "willingness to accept" OR WTA OR "preference assessment" OR "preference*" OR "benefit transfer*" OR "value transfer*" OR "non-monetary valuation" OR "monetary valuation" OR "elicitation method*" OR "value elicitation" OR PA-BAT OR "Trade-offs" OR "discourse analysis" OR "stakeholder workshop*" OR "interview*" OR "questionnaire*" OR "mental model*" OR "focus group*" OR "concept mapping" OR "Q methodology" OR "Q-methodology" OR "Q study" OR "Q-study" OR "bayesian belief network*" OR BN OR BBN OR "participatory GIS" OR "PPGIS" OR "PGIS" OR "narrative method*" OR "narrative approach*" OR ARIES OR "InVEST model*" OR "biophysical model*" OR "bio-physical model*" OR "biophysical valu*" OR "bio-physical valu*" OR "global environmental flow" OR Mapnat OR "MARXAN" OR "MEB" OR "Ecosystem service map*" OR "ES map*" OR "Ecological importance" OR "Spatial proxy model*" OR ESTIMAP OR GISCAM OR "Cultural Health Index" OR

		<p>"Environmental importance" OR "POLYSCAPE" OR "ecosystem service quantification" OR "ES quantification" OR "ecosystem service modeling" OR "ES modeling" OR "service providing unit" OR "ecosystem service supply" OR "ES supply" OR "ecosystem service delivery" OR "ES delivery" OR "species richness" OR "biodiversity index" OR "species diversity" OR "ecosystem accounting" OR "contingent valuation" OR "choice experiment*" OR "conjoint analysis" OR "random utility" OR "RUM" OR "Marginal Utility" OR "Lancasters Characteristics demand theory" OR "Marginal rate of substitution" OR "choice model" OR "stated preferences" OR "deliberative valuation" OR "role playing game*" OR "social assessment for protected areas" OR "socio-cultural valuation" OR "expert * elicitation" OR "Afrocentric metho*" OR "Biocultural Methods" OR SAPA OR "participatory mapping" OR "social importance" OR "socio-economic importance" OR "socio-cultural importance" OR "social preferences" OR "Hypothetical policy scenario" OR "Willingness to pay" OR "Willingness to accept" OR "Compensation" OR "Nonmarket valuation survey" OR "Individual welfare change" OR "Equivalent variation of welfare" OR "Compensatory variation of welfare" OR "Multiattribute model*" OR "multi-attribute model" OR "Discrete choice modelling" OR "Final mixture model" OR "Latent Class Model" OR "LCM" OR "Random Parameter Logit Model" OR RPLM OR "Mixed Logit Model" OR "alternative specific conditional logit" OR hedonic OR "travel cost" OR "cost-based" OR "cost-effectiveness" OR "production function" OR "shadow pric*" OR "Health valuation" OR "Photo Elicitation" OR "Photo-Elicitation" OR "replacement cost*" OR "averting behavior" OR "economic importance" OR "livelihood assess*" OR "market price*" OR "market valu*" OR "time use" OR "mitigating cost*" OR "preventive expenditure*" OR "cost of illness" OR "participant observation" OR "observe behavior" OR "observe practice*" OR "ritua*" OR "ceremon*" OR "cost-benefit" OR "cost benefit" OR "benefit cost" OR "benefit-cost" OR "MCA" OR "multicriteria analysis" OR "MCDA" OR "multicriteria decision analysis" OR "integrated valuation" OR "deliberative decision making" OR "business accounting" OR "corporate accounting" OR "profit and loss account*" OR ESG OR "Consensus analysis" OR "Natural Capital Accounting" OR "SolVES" OR "inclusive valuation" OR "integrated model*" OR "participatory decision*" OR "Deliberative integration")</p>
6	Methods_A	<p>TS = (Valuation OR WTP OR "willingness to pay" OR "willingness to accept" OR WTA OR "preference assessment" OR "preference*" OR "benefit transfer*" OR "value transfer*" OR "non-monetary valuation" OR "monetary valuation" OR "elicitation method*" OR "value elicitation" OR PA-BAT OR "Trade-offs")</p>
7	Methods_B	<p>TS = ("discourse analysis" OR "stakeholder workshop*" OR "interview*" OR "questionnaire*" OR "mental model*" OR "focus group*" OR "concept mapping" OR "Q methodology" OR "Q-methodology" OR "Q study" OR "Q-study" OR "bayesian belief network*" OR BN OR BBN OR "participatory GIS" OR "PPGIS" OR "PGIS" OR "narrative method*" OR "narrative approach*")</p>
8	Methods_Family1	<p>TS = (ARIES OR "INVEST model*" OR "biophysical model*" OR "bio-physical model*" OR "biophysical valu*" OR "bio-physical valu*" OR "global environmental flow" OR Mapnat OR "MARXAN" OR "MEB" OR "Ecosystem service map*" OR "ES map*" OR "Ecological importance" OR "Spatial proxy model*" OR ESTIMAP OR GISCAME OR "Cultural Health Index" OR "Environmental importance" OR "POLYSCAPE" OR "ecosystem service quantification" OR "ES quantification" OR "ecosystem service modeling" OR "ES modeling" OR "service providing unit" OR "ecosystem service supply" OR "ES supply" OR "ecosystem service delivery" OR "ES delivery" OR "species richness" OR "biodiversity index" OR "species diversity" OR "ecosystem accounting")</p>
9	Methods_Family2	<p>TS = ("contingent valuation" OR "choice experiment*" OR "conjoint analysis" OR "random utility" OR "RUM" OR "Marginal Utility" OR "Lancaster's Characteristics demand theory" OR "Marginal rate of substitution" OR "choice model" OR "stated preferences" OR "deliberative valuation" OR "role playing game*" OR "social assessment for protected areas" OR "socio-cultural valuation" OR "expert * elicitation" OR "Afrocentric metho*" OR "Biocultural Methods" OR SAPA OR "participatory mapping" OR "social importance" OR "socio-economic importance" OR "socio-cultural importance" OR "social preferences" OR "Hypothetical policy scenario" OR "Willingness to pay" OR "Willingness to accept" OR "Compensation" OR "Nonmarket valuation survey" OR "Individual welfare change" OR "Equivalent variation of welfare" OR "Compensatory variation of welfare" OR "Multiattribute model*" OR "multi-attribute model" OR "Discrete choice modelling" OR "Final mixture model" OR "Latent Class Model" OR "LCM" OR "Random Parameter Logit Model" OR RPLM OR "Mixed Logit Model" OR "alternative specific conditional logit")</p>
10	Methods_Family3	<p>TS = (hedonic OR "travel cost" OR "cost-based" OR "cost-effectiveness" OR "production function" OR "shadow pric*" OR "Health valuation" OR "Photo Elicitation" OR "Photo-Elicitation" OR "replacement cost*" OR "averting behavior" OR "economic importance" OR "livelihood assess*" OR "market price*" OR "market valu*" OR "time use" OR "mitigating cost*" OR "preventive expenditure*", OR "cost of illness" OR "participant observation" OR "observe behavior" OR "observe practice*" OR "ritua*" OR "ceremon*")</p>
11	Methods_Family4	<p>TS = ("cost-benefit" OR "cost benefit" OR "benefit cost" OR "benefit-cost" OR "MCA" OR "multicriteria analysis" OR "MCDA" OR "multicriteria decision analysis" OR "integrated valuation" OR "deliberative decision making" OR "business accounting" OR "corporate accounting" OR "profit and loss account*" OR ESG OR "Consensus analysis" OR "Deliberative * integration" OR "Natural Capital Accounting" OR "SolVES" OR "inclusive valuation" OR "integrated model*" OR "participatory decision*" OR "Deliberative integration")</p>
12	DECISION MAKING = #12 = #13 OR #14 OR #15	<p>TS=("provide information" OR "give information" OR "value formation" OR "value affirmation" OR "value expression" OR "value articulation" OR advoca* OR legitimat* OR "awareness raising" OR evaluation OR assessment* OR justif* OR "provide evidence" OR account* OR participat* OR decisive OR decision OR sustainab* OR restor* OR regulation OR conserv* OR degrad* OR negotiat* OR deliberat* OR "alternativ* format*" OR express* NOT "gene expression" OR prioritiz* OR prioritis* OR screen* OR rank* OR "alternative options" OR target* OR zoning OR planning OR policy OR decision* OR manage* OR extraction OR allocation OR distribution OR rights OR ownership OR licenc* OR permit* OR certif* OR quota*</p>

		OR responsibilit* OR rule* OR pric* OR "price-setting" OR payment* OR charge* OR fee OR fees OR tax* OR subsidy OR subsidies OR offset* OR off-set* OR compensat* OR "damage* assessment" OR NRDA OR litigat* OR liabilit*)
13	Purpose_Informative	TS=("provide information" OR "give information" OR "value formation" OR "value affirmation" OR "value expression" OR "value articulation" OR advoca* OR legitimat* OR "awareness raising" OR evaluation OR assessment* OR justif* OR "provide evidence" OR account* OR participat*)
14	Purpose_Decisive	TS=(decisive OR decision OR sustainab* OR restor* OR regulation OR conserv* OR degrad* OR negotiat* OR deliberat* OR "alternativ* formulat*" OR express* NOT "gene expression" OR prioritiz* OR prioritis* OR screen* OR rank* OR "alternative options" OR target* OR zoning OR planning OR policy OR decision* OR manage* OR extraction OR allocation OR distribution OR rights OR ownership OR licenc* OR permit* OR certif* OR quota* OR responsibilit* OR rule*)
15	Purpose_Technical	TS=(pric* OR "price-setting" OR payment* OR charge* OR fee OR fees OR tax* OR subsidy OR subsidies OR offset* OR off-set* OR compensat* OR "damage* assessment" OR NRDA OR litigat* OR liabilit*)
16	Nature_Biodiversity	TS=(nature NOT "nature of" NOT "by its nature" OR biodiversity OR marine OR terrestrial OR forest* NOT "random forest" OR woodland* OR grassland* OR savanna* OR shrubland* OR peatland OR ecosystem* OR lake* OR river* OR sea OR ocean* OR meadow* OR heathland* OR mires OR bog* OR tundra OR biosphere OR desert* OR mountain* OR "natural resource*" OR estuar* OR fjord* OR fauna OR flora OR soil* OR "coastal waters" OR "wetland*" OR "freshwater" OR "marshland" OR "marches" OR "dryland*" OR seascape* OR landscape* OR "coast*" OR "arable land*" OR "agricultural land*" OR "natural environment*" OR "environmental resource*" OR "agroforest*" OR "agro-forest*" OR "plantation*" OR "protected areas" OR chaparral)
17	Corpus_Ch3	#1 AND #5 AND #12 AND #16
18	C1_Method A	#17 AND #6
19	C2_Method B	#17 AND #7
20	C3_Method_Family1	#17 AND #8
21	C3_Method_Family2	#17 AND #9
22	C4_Method_Family3	#17 AND #10
23	C5_Method_Family4	#17 AND #11
24	C6_Value_TYPE1	#17 AND #2
25	C7_Value_TYPE2	#17 AND #3
26	C8_Value_TYPE3	#17 AND #4
27	CORPUS_Ch4	#1 AND #5 AND #16

